

Supplementary Information

2D and 3D Anticancer properties of C2-functionalised glucosamine-Pt(IV) prodrugs based on cisplatin scaffold

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Synthetic procedures

1,3,4,6-Tetra-O-acetyl-2-azido-2-deoxy-D-glucopyranoside (6)

A solution of NaN_3 (8.94 g, 137 mmol) in H_2O (22 mL) was cooled to 0°C and stirred for 5 mins and DCM (40 mL) was added. The mixture was stirred vigorously and Tf_2O (4.68 mL, 27.90 mmol) added over a period of 5 mins, and the reaction stirred at 0°C for 2 h. The organic phase was separated, and the aqueous phase was washed with DCM (35 mL). The combined organic phases were washed with saturated sodium carbonate solution. The total volume of TfN_3 in DCM was 75 mL, and this reagent solution was used without further purification. **5** (3.0 g, 13.95 mmol) was dissolved in H_2O (45 mL) and treated with solid K_2CO_3 (2.88 g, 20.93 mmol) and CuSO_4 (21 mg, 132 mmol). Methanol (90 mL) was added followed by the dropwise addition of the freshly prepared TfN_3 solution. Methanol was added until the solution was homogeneous, and the reaction was then stirred overnight at room temperature. The solvent was removed under vacuum and the residue was redissolved in pyridine (75 mL). This solution was then cooled to 0°C and Ac_2O (45 mL) was added, and the mixture was allowed to stir at room temperature overnight. Solvent was removed under vacuum and the residue was redissolved in EtOAc (300 mL) the organic phase was washed with saturated CuSO_4 solution (200 mL $\times$ 2) and saturated NaHCO_3 solution (200 mL) and the organic phase was dried with Na_2SO_4 and filtered. The solvent was removed under vacuum to give a residue which was purified by column chromatography (EtOAc: Petroleum ether=3:7) to give the product as a colourless syrup (3.848 g, 10.31 mmol, 74%). ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 6.27 (d, $J = 3.7$ Hz, 0.37H, H-1 α), 5.54 (d, $J = 8.6$ Hz, 0.63H, H-1 β), 5.43 (dd, $J = 10.4, 9.5$ Hz, 0.39H, H-3 α), 5.12 – 4.99 (m, 1.6H, H-3 β , H-4), 4.27 (dt, $J = 12.6, 4.5$ Hz, 1H, H-6), 4.08 – 4.00 (m, 1.38H, H-5 α , H-6'), 3.79 (ddd, $J = 9.7, 4.5, 2.1$ Hz, 0.61H, H-5 β), 3.65 (ddd, $J = 8.6, 5.8, 2.1$ Hz, 0.98H, H-2), 2.18 – 1.99 (m, 12H, 4 x CH_3 of OAc) ppm.

NMR data is in agreement with the data reported in the literature [Cheng, J.; Zhao, W.; Yao, H.; Shen, Y.; Zhang, Y.; Li, Y.Z.; Qi, Q.; Wongprasert, K.; Tang, Y.J. Discovery of 4,6- O-Thenylidene- β -D-Glucopyranoside-(2''-Acetamido, 3''-Acetyl-Di- S-5-Fluorobenzothiazole/5-Fluorobenzoxazole)-4'-Demethylepipodophyllotoxin as Potential Less Toxic Antitumor Candidate Drugs by Reducing DNA Damage and Less Inhibition of PI3K. *J Med Chem* **2020**, *63*, 2877–2893, doi:10.1021/acs.jmedchem.9b01354].

N-(1,3,4,6-Tetra-O-acetyl-2-deoxy-D-glucopyranosyl-1,2,3-triazol-4-yl)-propanoic acid (7)

6 (0.989 g, 2.649 mmol, 1.3 equiv.) and 4-pentynoic acid (0.2 g, 2.03 mmol) were dissolved in a mixture of tetrahydrofuran (6 ml), tert-Butanol (6 mL) and deionised water (4 mL). Separately, copper(II) sulphate pentahydrate (0.1 g, 0.40 mmol) and sodium ascorbate (0.161 g, 0.815 mmol) were dissolved in deionised water (2 mL), added to reaction flask and allowed to stir at r.t. overnight (16 h). The solvent was removed *in vacuo* and the residue was dissolved in DCM (15 mL) and washed with brine (2 x 20 mL). The organic phase was dried with MgSO_4 , filtered and the solvent was evaporated. The crude product was purified by column chromatography (1:1, petroleum ether : ethyl acetate) to yield a white solid (0.566 g, 1.20 mmol, 59%). $R_f = 0.18$ (95:5 DCM : MeOH). ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.47 (s, 0.52H, triaz-H α), 7.45 (s, 1H, triaz-H β), 6.36 (d, $J = 3.6$ Hz, 0.51H, H-1 α), 6.18 (d, $J = 8.8$ Hz, 1H, H-1 β), 5.92 (dd, $J = 11.4, 9.2$ Hz, 0.61H, H-3 α), 5.77 (dd, $J = 10.8, 9.2$ Hz, 1H, H-3 β), 5.26 (dd, $J = 10.2, 9.3$ Hz, 0.64H, H-4 α), 5.20 (dd, $J = 10.1, 9.3$ Hz, 1H, H-4 β), 5.13 (dd, $J = 11.4, 3.6$ Hz, 0.55H, H-2 α), 4.67 (dd, $J =$

10.8, 8.8 Hz, 1H, H-2 β), 4.40 – 4.32 (m, 1.51H, H-6 α , H-6 β), 4.20 (ddd, J = 10.3, 4.0, 2.3 Hz, 0.55H, H-5 α), 4.13 (ddd, J = 19.2, 12.5, 2.2 Hz, 1.54H, H-6' α , H-6' β), 4.07 (ddd, J = 10.1, 4.4, 2.2 Hz, 1H, H-5 β), 3.01 (q, J = 6.9 Hz, 3H, α/β triaz-CH₂), 2.74 (t, J = 6.9 Hz, 3H, α/β CH₂CO), 2.11 (s, 1.5H, α CH₃ of OAc), 2.10 (d, J = 2.2 Hz, 4.5H, α CH₃ of OAc, β CH₃ of OAc), 2.06 (s, 1.5H, α CH₃ of OAc), 2.03 (s, 3H, β CH₃ of OAc), 1.97 (s, 3H, β CH₃ of OAc), 1.85 (d, J = 3.5 Hz, 4.5H, β CH₃ of OAc, α CH₃ of OAc) ppm. ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 176.68 (COOH), 170.75 (α CO of OAc), 170.74 (β CO of OAc), 170.17 (α CO of OAc), 169.76 (β CO of OAc), 169.48 (α CO of OAc), 169.44 (β CO of OAc), 168.40 (β CO of OAc), 168.08 (α CO of OAc), 146.65 (triaz-C α), 146.49 (triaz-C β), 121.74 (triaz-CH β), 120.67 (triaz-CH α), 91.69 (C-1 β), 90.20 (C-1 α), 73.03 (C-5 β), 72.10 (C-3 β), 69.98 (C-5 α), 68.92 (C-3 α), 68.31 (C-4 β), 68.20 (C-4 α), 62.76 (C-2 β), 61.54 (C-6 β), 61.47 (C-6 α), 61.13 (C-2 α), 33.43 (α/β CH₂CO), 20.83 (CH₃ of OAc), 20.80 (2 x CH₃ of OAc), 20.78 (CH₃ of OAc), 20.68 (CH₃ of OAc), 20.65 (CH₃ of OAc), 20.60 (α/β triaz-CH₂), 20.41 (CH₃ of OAc), 20.30 (CH₃ of OAc) ppm. IR (ATR) 3141.55, 1753.04, 1736.47, 1367.40, 1207.16, 1026.92, 897.06 cm⁻¹. HR-MS (+): m/z calcd for C₁₉H₂₅N₃O₁₁ + H⁺ [M+H]⁺ 472.1567, found 472.1607. HR-MS (+): m/z calcd for C₁₉H₂₅N₃O₁₁ + Na⁺ [M+Na]⁺ 494.1387, found 494.1431.

N-(1,3,4,6-Tetra-*O*-acetyl-2-deoxy-*D*-glucopyranosyl-1,2,3-triazol-4-yl)-(3-oxopropyl-(oxy(2,5-dioxopyrrolidin-1-yl))) (**8**)

7 (0.120 g, 0.254 mmol) was added to a flask with NHS (0.035 g, 0.305 mmol, 1.2 equiv.), purged with N₂ and dissolved in dry DCM. EDCI (0.058 g, 0.305 mmol, 1.2 equiv.) was dissolved in DCM and added *via* cannula. The reaction was stirred overnight at room temperature. The DCM was washed with 0.1M HCl, brine and dried with Na₂SO₄. The solvent was filtered and evaporated to yield a white solid which was used without further purification (0.130 g, 0.228 mmol, 89%) (The ratio of alpha:beta was 1:0.51). R_f = 0.69 (95:5 DCM : MeOH). ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.65 (s, 1H, triaz-H β), 7.63 (s, 0.84H, triaz-H α), 6.31 (d, J = 3.5 Hz, 0.81H, H-1 α), 6.10 (d, J = 8.8 Hz, 1H, H-1 β), 5.88 (dd, J = 11.4, 9.2 Hz, 0.86H, H-3 α), 5.71 (dd, J = 10.8, 9.2 Hz, 1H, H-3 β), 5.19 (ddd, J = 21.6, 10.1, 9.3 Hz, 1.93H, H-4 β , H-4 α), 5.09 (dd, J = 11.4, 3.6 Hz, 0.88H, H-2 α), 4.66 (dd, J = 10.8, 8.8 Hz, 1H, H-2 β), 4.32 (ddd, J = 19.6, 12.5, 4.2 Hz, 1.9H, H-6 α , H-6 β), 4.18 (ddd, J = 10.3, 3.9, 2.3 Hz, 0.89H, H-5 α), 4.09 (ddd, J = 18.8, 12.5, 2.2 Hz, 1.91H, H-6' α , H-6' β), 4.03 (ddd, J = 10.2, 4.3, 2.2 Hz, 1H, H-5 β), 3.16 – 3.07 (m, 3.67H, α/β triaz-CH₂), 3.00 – 2.89 (m, 3.76H, α/β CH₂CO), 2.81 (s, 7.52H, α/β CH₂CH₂-Succ), 2.07 (s, 2.57H, α CH₃ of OAc), 2.06 (s, 5.43H, α/β CH₃ of OAc), 2.01 (s, 2.54H, α CH₃ of OAc), 1.99 (s, 3H, β CH₃ of OAc), 1.92 (s, 3H, β CH₃ of OAc), 1.81 (s, 3H, β CH₃ of OAc), 1.79 (s, 2.35H, α CH₃ of OAc) ppm. ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 170.61 (α CO of OAc), 170.59 (β CO of OAc), 169.87 (α CO of OAc), 169.60 (β CO of OAc), 169.40 (α CO of OAc), 169.32 (β CO of OAc), 169.27 (α/β CO-Succ), 168.30 (β CO of OAc), 168.01 (α CO of OAc), 167.72 (CO β), 167.68 (CO α), 145.20 (triaz-C α), 145.16 (triaz-C β), 121.91 (triaz-CH β), 121.20 (triaz-CH α), 91.59 (C-1 β), 90.07 (C-1 α), 72.84 (C-5 β), 71.97 (C-3 β), 69.78 (C-5 α), 68.85 (C-3 α), 68.36 (C-4 α), 68.12 (C-4 β), 62.61 (C-2 β), 61.42 (C-6 β), 61.40 (C-6 α), 60.96 (C-2 α), 31.16 (β CH₂CO), 31.13 (α CH₂CO), 25.64 (β CH₂CH₂-Succ), 25.63 (α CH₂CH₂-Succ), 21.10 (α triaz-CH₂), 21.05 (β triaz-CH₂), 20.73 (β CH₃ of OAc), 20.71 (α CH₃ of OAc), 20.69 (α CH₃ of OAc), 20.59 (β CH₃ of OAc), 20.57 (α CH₃ of OAc), 20.50 (β CH₃ of OAc), 20.31 (α CH₃ of OAc), 20.21 (β CH₃ of OAc) ppm. IR (ATR) 2959.88, 1731.79, 1366.73, 1201.79, 1067.81, 1043.20, 813.86 cm⁻¹. HR-MS (+): m/z calcd for C₂₃H₂₈N₄O₁₃ + H⁺ [M+H]⁺ 569.1731, found 569.1800. HR-MS (+): m/z calcd for C₂₃H₂₈N₄O₁₃ + Na⁺ [M+Na]⁺ 591.1551, found 591.1631.

Methyl-N-(3,4,6-tri-*O*-acetyl-2-deoxy- α -*D*-glucopyranosyl-1,2,3-triazol-4-yl)-propanoic acid (**14**)

13 (0.469 g, 1.35 mmol) and 4-pentynoic acid (0.264 g, 2.7 mmol, 2 equiv.) were dissolved in t-BuOH (12mL), H₂O (12mL) and THF (12mL). CuSO₄ (195 mg) and NaAsc (275 mg) were added and allowed to stir overnight. Completion of the reaction was followed by TLC (DCM:MeOH. 9:1). The solvent was then removed *in vacuo* and the resulting residue was redissolved in DCM and washed with brine. The organic layer was dried and filtered, and the crude product was purified by column chromatography (DCM:MeOH. 95:5). The pure product was obtained as a colourless oil (0.394 g, 0.888 mmol, 65%). R_f = 0.37 (95:5 DCM:MeOH). ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.57 (s, 1H, triaz-CH), 5.75 (dd, J = 11.2, 9.1 Hz, 1H, H-3), 5.18 (dd, J = 10.1, 9.2 Hz, 1H, H-4), 5.01 (dd, J = 11.3, 3.4 Hz, 1H, H-2), 4.96 (d, J = 3.4 Hz, 1H,

H-1), 4.31 (dd, $J = 12.4, 4.7$ Hz, 1H, H-6), 4.16 (dd, $J = 12.3, 2.4$ Hz, 1H, H-6'), 4.11 (ddd, $J = 10.2, 4.7, 2.3$ Hz, 1H, H-5), 3.39 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 3.02 (t, $J = 7.3$ Hz, 2H, triaz-CH₂), 2.75 (t, $J = 7.4$ Hz, 2H, CH₂CO), 2.12 (s, 3H, CH₃ of OAc), 2.04 (s, 3H, CH₃ of OAc), 1.80 (s, 3H, CH₃ of OAc) ppm. ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 177.04 (CO), 170.79 (CO of OAc), 170.18 (CO of OAc), 169.55 (CO of OAc), 146.31 (triaz-C), 121.14 (triaz-CH), 98.10 (C-1), 69.41 (C-3), 68.77 (C-4), 67.88 (C-5), 62.29 (C-2), 61.94 (C-6), 55.77 (OCH₃), 33.51 (CH₂CO), 20.91 (triaz-CH₂), 20.85 (CH₃ of OAc), 20.68 (CH₃ of OAc), 20.35 (CH₃ of OAc) ppm. IR (ATR) 2943.14, 1739.49, 1367.31, 1217.89, 1032.28, 927.19, 733.50, 601.37 cm⁻¹. HR-MS (+): m/z calcd for C₁₈H₂₅N₃O₁₀ + H⁺ [M+H]⁺ 444.1618, found 444.1616. HR-MS (+): m/z calcd for C₁₈H₂₅N₃O₁₀ + Na⁺ [M+Na]⁺ 466.1438, found 466.1433.

Methyl-N-(3,4,6-tri-O-acetyl-2-deoxy- α -D-glucopyranosyl-1,2,3-triazol-4-yl)-(3-oxopropyl-(oxy(2,5-dioxopyrrolidin-1-yl))) (15)

14 (0.240 g, 0.541 mmol) and NHS (0.074 g, 0.649 mmol, 1.2 equiv.) were purged with N₂ and dissolved in anhydrous DCM (10 mL). A separate flask containing EDCI (0.124 g, 0.649 mmol, 1.2 equiv.) was also purged with N₂ and dissolved in anhydrous DCM (4 mL). This was added to the solution of **14** and NHS via cannula addition and the reaction was allowed to stir overnight at room temperature. The organic phase was washed with 0.1M HCl, dried, filtered and the solvent was evaporated and isolated as a white powder (0.267 g, 0.494 mmol, 91%). $R_f = 0.77$ (95:5 DCM:MeOH). ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.68 (s, 1H, triaz-CH), 5.74 (dd, $J = 11.2, 9.1$ Hz, 1H, H-3), 5.18 (dd, $J = 10.1, 9.2$ Hz, 1H, H-4), 5.02 (dd, $J = 11.2, 3.4$ Hz, 1H, H-2), 4.98 (d, $J = 3.4$ Hz, 1H, H-1), 4.32 (dd, $J = 12.3, 4.6$ Hz, 1H, H-6), 4.17 (dd, $J = 12.3, 2.4$ Hz, 1H, H-6'), 4.13 (ddd, $J = 10.3, 4.6, 2.4$ Hz, 1H, H-5), 3.40 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 3.15 (td, $J = 7.2, 2.4$ Hz, 2H, triaz-CH₂), 3.01 (td, $J = 7.2, 2.4$ Hz, 2H, CH₂CO), 2.83 (s, 4H, CH₂CH₂-succ), 2.12 (s, 3H, CH₃ of OAc), 2.04 (s, 3H, CH₃ of OAc), 1.81 (s, 3H, CH₃ of OAc) ppm. ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 170.78 (CO of OAc), 170.07 (CO of OAc), 169.57 (CO of OAc), 169.16 (CO succ x2), 167.80 (CO), 145.16 (triaz-C), 121.50 (triaz-CH), 98.13 (C-1), 69.49 (C-3), 68.90 (C-4), 67.84 (C-5), 62.30 (C-2), 61.96 (C-6), 55.80 (OCH₃), 31.12 (CH₂CO), 25.74 (CH₂CH₂-succ), 21.13 (triaz-CH₂), 20.87 (CH₃ of OAc), 20.72 (CH₃ of OAc), 20.42 (CH₃ of OAc) ppm. IR (ATR) 2962.23, 1731.98, 1366.80, 1204.22, 1029.25, 799.23 cm⁻¹. HR-MS (+): m/z calcd for C₂₂H₂₈N₄O₁₂ + H⁺ [M+H]⁺ 541.1782, found 541.1817. HR-MS (+): m/z calcd for C₂₂H₂₈N₄O₁₂ + Na⁺ [M+Na]⁺ 563.1601, found 563.1641.

Methyl-2-(2-bromoacetamido)-2-deoxy-3,4,6-tri-O-acetyl- α -D-glucopyranoside (16)

12 (2.305 g, 7.21 mmol) was purged with N₂ and dissolved in dry DCM (19 mL). NEt₃ (1.2 mL, 8.66 mmol, 1.2 equiv) was added and the solution was allowed to stir over ice. Bromoacetyl bromide (0.75 mL, 8.66 mmol, 1.2 equiv.) was diluted with dry DCM (5 mL) and added to the flask *via* cannula. The reaction was stirred overnight, and the crude product was extracted with 1M HCl, aqueous NaHCO₃, brine and dried with Na₂SO₄. Yielding a white solid (2.279 g, 5.176 mmol, 71%). $R_f = 0.73$ (petroleum ether: EtOAc 1:1). ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 6.56 (d, $J = 9.4$ Hz, 1H, NHCO), 5.25 (dd, $J = 10.7, 9.5$ Hz, 1H, H-3), 5.09 (t, $J = 10.2$ Hz, 1H, H-4), 4.74 (d, $J = 3.6$ Hz, 1H, H-1), 4.31 – 4.20 (m, 2H, H-2, H-6), 4.09 (dd, $J = 12.3, 2.4$ Hz, 1H, H-6'), 3.93 (ddd, $J = 10.1, 4.7, 2.3$ Hz, 1H, H-5), 3.78 (d, $J = 2.6$ Hz, 2H, CH₂Br), 3.41 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 2.08 (s, 3H, CH₃ of OAc), 2.01 (s, 3H, CH₃ of OAc), 1.99 (s, 3H, CH₃ of OAc) ppm. ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 171.17 (CO of OAc), 170.77 (CO of OAc), 169.43 (CO of OAc), 166.03 (NHCO), 98.04 (C-1), 70.93 (C-3), 68.15 (C-4), 67.78 (C-5), 62.02 (C-6), 55.65 (OCH₃), 52.58 (C-2), 28.45 (CH₂Br), 20.81 (2x CH₃ of OAc), 20.69 (CH₃ of OAc) ppm. IR (ATR) 3246.56, 1734.05, 1651.68, 1552.68, 1363.83, 1211.90, 1131.38, 1056.20, 1029.13, 924.95 cm⁻¹. HR-MS (+): m/z calcd for C₁₅H₂₂BrNO₉ + Na⁺ [M+Na]⁺ 462.0376, found 462.0319.

Methyl-2-(2-azidoacetamido)-2-deoxy-3,4,6-tri-O-acetyl- α -D-glucopyranoside (17)

16 (1.818 g, 4.12 mmol) and NaN₃ (0.536 g, 8.25 mmol, 2 equiv.) were dissolved in anhydrous DMF (24 mL) and refluxed at 80°C overnight. DMF was evaporated and the residue was redissolved in DCM and washed with cold water. The organic phase was dried with Na₂SO₄, filtered and dried *in vacuo* to yield a white solid (1.634 g, 4.06 mmol, 98%). $R_f = 0.72$ (petroleum ether: EtOAc 1:1). ¹H NMR (500 MHz,

CDCl₃) δ 6.50 (d, *J* = 9.5 Hz, 1H, NHCO), 5.25 (dd, *J* = 10.6, 9.5 Hz, 1H, H-3), 5.12 (t, *J* = 9.8 Hz, 1H, H-4), 4.74 (d, *J* = 3.6 Hz, 1H, H-1), 4.32 (ddd, *J* = 10.6, 9.5, 3.7 Hz, 1H, H-2), 4.25 (dd, *J* = 12.3, 4.6 Hz, 1H, H-6), 4.11 (dd, *J* = 12.3, 2.4 Hz, 1H, H-6'), 3.96 – 3.91 (m, 3H, H-5, CH₂N₃), 3.42 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 2.10 (s, 3H, CH₃ of OAc), 2.03 (s, 3H, CH₃ of OAc), 2.01 (s, 3H, CH₃ of OAc) ppm. ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 171.31 (CO of OAc), 170.81 (CO of OAc), 169.47 (CO of OAc), 166.84 (NHCO), 98.10 (C-1), 71.27 (C-3), 68.16 (C-4), 67.78 (C-5), 62.08 (C-6), 55.63 (OCH₃), 52.66 (CH₂N₃), 52.07 (C-2), 20.85 (CH₃ of OAc), 20.82 (CH₃ of OAc), 20.73 (CH₃ of OAc) ppm. IR (ATR) 3332.36, 2104.64, 1736.94, 1670.34, 1542.60, 1368.04, 1217.17, 1030.83, 923.96 cm⁻¹. HR-MS (+): *m/z* calcd for C₁₅H₂₂N₄O₉ + H⁺ [M+H]⁺ 403.1465, found 403.1417. HR-MS (+): *m/z* calcd for C₁₅H₂₂N₄O₉ + Na⁺ [M+Na]⁺ 425.1284, found 425.1237.

Methyl-N-(2-deoxy-3,4,6-tri-O-acetyl-α-D-glucopyranosyl)-2-acetamido-1,2,3-triazol-4-yl)]-propanoic acid (18)

17 (0.525 g, 1.304 mmol) and 4-Pentynoic acid (0.191 g, 1.956 mmol, 1.5 equiv.) were dissolved in 15 mL each of t-BuOH and H₂O. Sodium ascorbate (0.183 g, 0.92 mmol) and CuSO₄·5H₂O (0.140 g, 0.57 mmol) were added to the solution. This was allowed to stir at room temperature overnight. The solvent was removed *in vacuo* and the residue was redissolved in DCM and washed with brine. The organic phase was dried with Na₂SO₄ and filtered. The crude product was purified with column chromatography (DCM:MeOH 9:1) to yield a white solid (0.267 g, 0.723 mmol, 41%). *R_f* = 0.78 (90:10 DCM:MeOH). ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.55 (s, 1H, triaz-CH), 6.72 (d, *J* = 9.0 Hz, 1H, NHCO), 5.16 (t, *J* = 9.9 Hz, 1H, H-3), 5.06 (t, *J* = 9.8 Hz, 1H, H-4), 4.96 (q, *J* = 16.3 Hz, 2H, NHCOCH₂), 4.71 (d, *J* = 3.5 Hz, 1H, H-1), 4.30 (td, *J* = 10.1, 3.6 Hz, 1H, H-2), 4.24 (dd, *J* = 12.4, 4.7 Hz, 1H, H-6), 4.07 (dd, *J* = 12.3, 2.2 Hz, 1H, H-6'), 3.92 (ddd, *J* = 10.0, 4.5, 2.3 Hz, 1H, H-5), 3.37 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 3.01 (br s, 2H, triaz-CH₂), 2.73 (br s, 2H, CH₂CO), 2.07 (s, 3H, CH₃ of OAc), 2.00 (s, 3H, CH₃ of OAc), 1.93 (s, 3H, CH₃ of OAc) ppm. ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 176.19 (COOH), 171.49 (CO of OAc), 170.85 (CO of OAc), 169.52 (CO of OAc), 165.92 (NHCOCH₂), 146.82 (triaz-C), 123.44 (triaz-CH), 98.04 (C-1), 71.25 (C-3), 68.17 (C-4), 67.69 (C-5), 62.09 (C-6), 55.68 (OCH₃), 52.56 (C-2), 52.24 (NHCOCH₂), 33.37 (CH₂CO), 20.81 (2x CH₃ of OAc), 20.72 (triaz-CH₂), 20.67 (CH₃ of OAc) ppm. IR (ATR) 2952.36, 1738.18, 1548.62, 1366.16, 1220.66, 1031.59, 732.92, 553.38 cm⁻¹. HR-MS (+): *m/z* calcd for C₂₀H₂₈N₄O₁₁ + H⁺ [M+H]⁺ 501.1833, found 501.1783. HR-MS (+): *m/z* calcd for C₂₀H₂₈N₄O₁₁ + Na⁺ [M+Na]⁺ 523.1652, found 523.1594.

Methyl-N-(2-deoxy-3,4,6-tri-O-acetyl-α-D-glucopyranosyl)-2-acetamido-1,2,3-triazol-4-yl-(3-oxopropyl-(oxy(2,5-dioxopyrrolidin-1-yl))) (19)

18 (0.179 g, 0.357 mmol) was added to a flask with NHS (0.049 g, 0.429 mmol, 1.2 equiv.), purged with N₂ and dissolved in dry DCM. EDCI (0.082 g, 0.429 mmol, 1.2 equiv.) was dissolved in DCM and added *via* cannula. The reaction was stirred overnight at room temperature. The DCM was washed with 0.1M HCl, brine and dried with Na₂SO₄. The solvent was filtered and evaporated to yield a white solid which was used without further purification (0.176 g, 0.294 mmol, 82%). *R_f* = 0.64 (95:5 DCM:MeOH). ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.59 (s, 1H, triaz-CH), 6.14 (d, *J* = 9.2 Hz, 1H, NHCO), 5.10 (dt, *J* = 26.2, 9.5 Hz, 2H, H-3, H-4), 4.98 (q, *J* = 16.4 Hz, 2H, NHCOCH₂), 4.71 (d, *J* = 3.7 Hz, 1H, H-1), 4.29 (ddd, *J* = 10.3, 9.3, 3.7 Hz, 1H, H-2), 4.24 (dd, *J* = 12.4, 4.7 Hz, 1H, H-6), 4.08 (dd, *J* = 12.4, 2.4 Hz, 1H, H-6'), 3.90 (ddd, *J* = 9.8, 4.6, 2.3 Hz, 1H, H-5), 3.37 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 3.21 (t, *J* = 7.1 Hz, 2H, triaz-CH₂), 3.05 (dd, *J* = 10.6, 4.1 Hz, 2H, CH₂CO), 2.84 (s, 4H, CH₂CH₂-succ), 2.09 (s, 3H, CH₃ of OAc), 2.01 (s, 3H, CH₃ of OAc), 1.98 (s, 3H, CH₃ of OAc) ppm. ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 171.27 (CO of OAc), 170.82 (CO of OAc), 169.47 (CO of OAc), 169.18 (CO succ x2), 168.06 (CO), 165.36 (NHCOCH₂), 145.74 (triaz-C), 123.38 (triaz-CH), 97.97 (C-1), 71.25 (C-3), 68.09 (C-4), 67.72 (C-5), 62.05 (C-6), 55.70 (OCH₃), 52.89 (NHCOCH₂), 52.37 (C-2), 30.94 (CH₂CO), 25.72 (CH₂CH₂-succ), 21.06 (triaz-CH₂), 20.86 (CH₃ of OAc), 20.81 (CH₃ of OAc), 20.72 (CH₃ of OAc) ppm. IR (ATR) 2960.39, 1731.85, 1542.01, 1366.05, 1208.29, 1031.45, 806.41, 647.24 cm⁻¹. HR-MS (+): *m/z* calcd for C₂₄H₃₁N₅O₁₃ + H⁺ [M+H]⁺ 598.1997, found 598.2036. HR-MS (+): *m/z* calcd for C₂₄H₃₁N₅O₁₃ + Na⁺ [M+Na]⁺ 620.1816, found 620.1860.

Methyl-N-(2-deoxy-α-D-glucopyranosyl-1,2,3-triazol-4-yl)-propanoic acid (20)

18 (0.297 g, 0.593 mmol) was dissolved in MeOH (6 mL) and H₂O (3 mL). NEt₃ (0.1 mL) was added, and the reaction was stirred at 40°C overnight. The progress was monitored using TLC (90:10 DCM:MeOH). The solvent was dried, and the residue was redissolved in H₂O and stirred with amberlite H⁺ resin for 1 hour. The amberlite H⁺ was filtered and the filtrate was dried by lyophilisation. Yielding a fluffy white solid (Yield 0.219 g, 0.585 mmol, 98%). ¹H NMR (500 MHz, D₂O) δ 7.80 (s, 1H, triaz-CH), 5.24 (s, 2H, NHCOCH₂), 4.77 (d, *J* = 3.6 Hz, 1H, H-1), 3.96 (dd, *J* = 10.6, 3.6 Hz, 1H, H-2), 3.86 (dd, *J* = 12.3, 2.3 Hz, 1H, H-6), 3.74 (ddd, *J* = 16.1, 11.5, 7.3 Hz, 2H, H-3, H-6'), 3.67 (ddd, *J* = 10.0, 5.4, 2.3 Hz, 1H, H-5), 3.46 (t, *J* = 9.1 Hz, 1H, H-4), 3.38 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 2.98 (t, *J* = 7.3 Hz, 2H, triaz-CH₂), 2.66 (t, *J* = 7.3 Hz, 2H, CH₂CO) ppm. ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, D₂O) δ 179.02 (CO), 168.20 (NHCO), 147.20 (triaz-C), 124.52 (triaz-CH), 97.90 (C-1), 71.65 (C-5), 71.14 (C-3), 69.87 (C-4), 60.50 (C-6), 55.15 (OCH₃), 53.81 (C-2), 51.83 (NHCOCH₂), 34.53 (CH₂CO), 20.73 (triaz-CH₂) ppm. IR (ATR) 3287.05, 1664.63, 1562.97, 1562.97, 1114.43, 1050.55, 1030.28 cm⁻¹. HR-MS (+): *m/z* calcd for C₁₄H₂₂N₄O₈ + H⁺ [M+H]⁺ 375.1516, found 375.1510. HR-MS (+): *m/z* calcd for C₁₄H₂₂N₄O₈ + Na⁺ [M+Na]⁺ 397.1335, found 397.1327.

Methyl-N-(2-deoxy-α-D-glucopyranosyl-1,2,3-triazol-4-yl)-(3-oxopropyl-(oxy(2,5-dioxopyrrolidin-1-yl))) (**21**)

20 (0.05g, 0.1335 mmol) and TSTU (0.044 g, 0.1469 mmol, 1.1 equiv.) were added to a flask, flushed with N₂ and dissolved in DMF (7 mL). NEt₃ (0.02 mL, 0.1469 mmol, 1.1 equiv.) was added to the solution and the reaction was allowed to stir at room temperature for 20 minutes. Checking reaction progress by TLC (60:35:5 DCM:MeOH:H₂O). The DMF was evaporated, and the residue was washed with DCM, collecting the precipitating product by centrifugation. The pink/white solid was washed with diethyl ether and dried *in vacuo* (Yield 0.049 g, 0.103 mmol, 79%). *R_f* = 0.83 (DCM:MeOH:H₂O 60:35:5). ¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO) δ 8.33 (d, *J* = 8.4 Hz, 1H, NHCO), 7.86 (s, 1H, triaz-CH), 5.13 – 5.05 (m, 2H, NHCOCH₂), 5.04 (d, *J* = 5.7 Hz, 1H, OH of C-4), 4.90 (d, *J* = 5.6 Hz, 1H, OH of C-3), 4.56 (d, *J* = 3.5 Hz, 1H, H-1), 4.53 (t, *J* = 5.9 Hz, 1H, OH of C-6), 3.71 – 3.62 (m, 2H, H-2, H-6), 3.51 – 3.45 (m, 2H, H-6', H-3), 3.37 – 3.34 (m, 1H, overlaps with H₂O, H-5), 3.27 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 3.18 – 3.12 (m, 1H, H-4), 3.08 – 3.04 (m, 2H, CH₂CO), 2.99 (dd, *J* = 11.3, 4.2 Hz, 2H, triaz-CH₂), 2.81 (s, 4H, CH₂CH₂-succ) ppm. ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, DMSO) δ 170.22 (CO succ x2), 168.36 (CO), 165.58 (CONH), 144.10 (triaz-C), 123.85 (triaz-CH), 97.74 (C-1), 72.80 (C-5), 70.83 (C-3), 70.65 (C-4), 60.75 (C-6), 54.33 (OCH₃), 54.04 (C-2), 51.49 (NHCOCH₂), 29.80 (CH₂CO), 25.46 (CH₂CH₂-Succ), 20.27 (triaz-CH₂) ppm. IR (ATR) 3285.14, 1732.92, 1667.17, 1559.92, 1208.18, 1024.06, 646.62 cm⁻¹. HR-MS (+): *m/z* calcd for C₁₈H₂₅N₅O₁₀ + H⁺ [M+H]⁺ 472.1680, found 472.1696. HR-MS (+): *m/z* calcd for C₁₈H₂₅N₅O₁₀ + Na⁺ [M+Na]⁺ 494.1499, found 494.1534.

Cis,cis,trans-[Pt_{IV}(NH₃)₂(7)(OH)Cl₂] (**1**)

8 (0.130 g, 0.2286 mmol) was added to a round bottom flask containing a suspension of oxoplatin (0.080 g, 0.239 mmol) in DMSO (6 mL) and stirred overnight at 60°C in the dark. The next morning, excess oxoplatin was filtered through cotton and the DMSO was evaporated by lyophilization. The oily residue was redissolved in acetone and the product was precipitated using diethyl ether. The residual solvent was then removed *in vacuo* yielding a yellow solid (0.122 g, 0.154 mmol, 67%). (The ratio of alpha:beta was 1:0.51). ¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO) δ 8.01 (s, 1H, triaz-CHβ), 7.92 (s, 0.54H, triaz-CHα), 6.35 (d, *J* = 8.7 Hz, 1H, H-1β), 6.26 (d, *J* = 3.5 Hz, 0.51H, H-1α), 6.14 – 5.78 (m, 10.5H, α/β NH₃, H-3β, H-3α), 5.36 (dd, *J* = 11.2, 3.5 Hz, 0.54H, H-2α), 5.19 (t, *J* = 9.85, 0.60H, H-4α), 5.09 (t, *J* = 9.7 Hz, 1H, H-4β), 4.90 (dd, *J* = 10.7, 8.7 Hz, 1H, H-2β), 4.35 (ddd, *J* = 10.1, 4.6, 2.3 Hz, 1H, H-5β), 4.32 – 4.27 (m, 0.64H, H-5α), 4.24 (m, 1.74H, H-6α, H-6β), 4.10 – 4.02 (m, 1.77H, H-6'α, H-6'β), 2.78 (t, *J* = 7.8, 3H, α/β triaz-CH₂), 2.45 – 2.39 (m, 3H, α/β CH₂CO), 2.10 (s, 1.5H, α CH₃ of OAc), 2.03 (d, *J* = 1.6 Hz, 4.5H, α/β CH₃ of OAc), 2.00 (s, 1.5H, α CH₃ of OAc), 1.99 (s, 3H, β CH₃ of OAc), 1.93 (s, 3H, β CH₃ of OAc), 1.80 (s, 3H, β CH₃ of OAc), 1.79 (s, 3H, α CH₃ of OAc) ppm. ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, DMSO) δ 179.73 (COO⁺Pt α), 179.70 (COO⁺Pt β), 170.05 (2x CO of OAc), 169.35 (CO of OAc), 169.28 (CO of OAc), 169.22 (CO of OAc), 168.91 (CO of OAc), 168.51 (CO of OAc), 168.29 (CO of OAc), 146.66 (triaz-Cα), 146.56 (triaz-Cβ), 122.11 (triaz-CHβ), 121.92 (triaz-CHα), 91.03 (C-1β), 89.54 (C-1α), 71.70 (C-5β), 71.50 (C-3β), 69.33 (C-

5 α), 68.82 (C-3 α), 68.00 (C-4 α), 67.90 (C-4 β), 61.65 (C-2 β), 61.44 (C-6 β), 61.22 (C-6 α), 59.66 (C-2 α), 36.17 (α CH₂CO), 36.09 (β CH₂CO), 21.85 (α/β triaz-CH₂), 20.55 (3x CH₃ of OAc), 20.39 (CH₃ of OAc), 20.37 (CH₃ of OAc) 20.28 (CH₃ of OAc), 20.11 (CH₃ of OAc), 20.02 (CH₃ of OAc) ppm. ¹⁹⁵Pt{¹H} NMR (108 MHz, DMSO) δ 1045.54 ppm. IR (ATR) 3220.55, 1747.64, 1623.98, 1367.12, 1212.66, 1043.50, 906.86 cm⁻¹. Elem. Anal. Calcd (%) for C₁₉H₃₁Cl₂N₅O₁₂Pt: C: 28.98, H: 3.97, N: 8.89; found C: 29.36, H: 4.33, N: 9.28. HR-MS (-): m/z calcd for C₁₉H₃₁Cl₂N₅O₁₂Pt – H⁻ [M-H]⁻ 786.4560, found 786.0913.

Cis,cis,trans-[Pt^{IV}(NH₃)₂(**14**)(OH)Cl₂] (**2**)

15 (0.236 g, 0.436 mmol) was added to a suspension of oxoplatin (0.153 g, 0.458 mmol, 1.05 equiv.) in DMSO (15 mL) and stirred at 55°C overnight. The resulting suspension was filtered, and the filtrate was lyophilized to remove the DMSO. The oily residue was washed then dissolved in acetone and precipitated with diethyl ether to yield a pale yellow powder (0.285 g, 0.375 mmol, 86%). ¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO) δ 7.81 (s, 1H, triaz-CH), 6.13 – 5.81 (br t, *J* = 51.65 Hz, 6H, 2x NH₃), 5.73 – 5.67 (m, 1H, H-3), 5.14 – 5.06 (m, 3H, H-4, H-1, H-2), 4.22 (dd, *J* = 12.3, 5.0 Hz, 1H, H-6), 4.11 (dd, *J* = 12.3, 2.4 Hz, 1H, H-6'), 4.06 (ddd, *J* = 10.2, 4.9, 2.4 Hz, 1H, H-5), 3.32 (s, 3H, OCH₃ overlaps with H₂O), 2.81 – 2.77 (m, 2H, triaz-CH₂), 2.46 – 2.42 (m, 2H, CH₂CO), 2.04 (s, 3H, CH₃ of OAc), 2.00 (s, 3H, CH₃ of OAc), 1.75 (s, 3H, CH₃ of OAc) ppm. ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, DMSO) δ 179.72 (CO), 170.08 (CO of OAc), 169.31 (CO of OAc), 169.22 (CO of OAc), 146.46 (triaz-C), 121.50 (triaz-CH), 97.12 (C-1), 69.08 (C-3), 68.52 (C-4), 67.07 (C-5), 61.75 (C-6), 60.86 (C-2), 55.01 (OCH₃), 36.13 (CH₂CO), 21.85 (triaz-CH₂), 20.53 (CH₃ of OAc), 20.38 (CH₃ of OAc), 20.06 (CH₃ of OAc) ppm. ¹⁹⁵Pt{¹H} NMR (108 MHz, DMSO) δ 1046.86 ppm. IR (ATR) 3217.18, 1744.63, 1624.51, 1367.45, 1224.71, 1040.54, 928.27 cm⁻¹. Elem. Anal. Calcd (%) for C₁₈H₃₁Cl₂N₅O₁₁Pt: C: 28.47, H: 4.11, N: 9.22; found C: 28.86, H: 4.45, N: 9.48. HR-MS (+): m/z calcd for C₁₈H₃₁Cl₂N₅O₁₁Pt + H⁺ [M+H]⁺ 759.1123, found 759.1141. HR-MS (+): m/z calcd for C₁₈H₃₁Cl₂N₅O₁₁Pt + Na⁺ [M+Na]⁺ 781.0943, found 781.0964.

Cis,cis,trans-[Pt^{IV}(NH₃)₂(**18**)(OH)Cl₂] (**3**)

19 (0.176 g, 0.294 mmol) was added to a suspension of oxoplatin (0.103 g, 0.309 mmol, 1.05 equiv.) in DMSO (10 mL) and stirred overnight at 60°C in the dark. The excess oxoplatin was filtered through cotton and the DMSO was lyophilized. The residue was redissolved in acetone and the product was precipitated with diethyl ether and dried with the Schlenk line to yield a pale yellow solid (0.197 g, 82%). ¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO) δ 8.52 (d, *J* = 9.2 Hz, 1H, NHCO), 7.80 (s, 1H, triaz-CH), 5.97 (br t, *J* = 49.9 Hz, 6H), 5.15 (dd, *J* = 10.9, 9.4 Hz, 1H, H-3), 5.07 – 4.98 (m, 2H, NHCOCH₂), 4.90 (t, *J* = 9.8 Hz, 1H, H-4), 4.75 (d, *J* = 3.4 Hz, 1H, H-1), 4.17 (dd, *J* = 12.4, 4.9 Hz, 1H, H-6), 4.14 – 4.09 (m, 1H, H-2), 4.04 (dd, *J* = 12.3, 2.3 Hz, 1H, H-6'), 3.93 (ddd, *J* = 10.1, 4.8, 2.4 Hz, 1H, H-5), 3.37 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 2.81 (t, *J* = 7.5 Hz, 2H, triaz-CH₂), 2.46 (t, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 2H, CH₂CO), 2.02 (s, 3H, CH₃ of OAc), 1.97 (s, 3H, CH₃ of OAc), 1.89 (s, 3H, CH₃ of OAc) ppm. ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, DMSO) δ 179.89 (COOPt), 170.16 (CO of OAc), 169.89 (CO of OAc), 169.34 (CO of OAc), 166.15 (NHCOCH₂), 146.11 (triaz-C), 123.79 (triaz-CH), 97.62 (C-1), 70.35 (C-3), 68.55 (C-4), 66.97 (C-5), 61.87 (C-6), 55.02 (OCH₃), 51.25 (NHCOCH₂), 51.09 (C-2), 36.14 (CH₂CO), 21.92 (triaz-CH₂), 20.55 (CH₃ of OAc), 20.44 (2x CH₃ of OAc) ppm. ¹⁹⁵Pt{¹H} NMR (108 MHz, DMSO) δ 1046.19 ppm. IR (ATR) 3231.16, 1743.14, 1675.08, 1558.18, 1366.47, 1226.87, 1034.87 cm⁻¹. Elem. Anal. Calcd (%) for C₂₀H₃₄Cl₂N₆O₁₂Pt: C: 29.42, H: 4.20, N: 10.29; found C: 29.86, H: 4.49, N: 9.95. HR-MS (+): m/z calcd for C₂₀H₃₄Cl₂N₆O₁₂Pt + H⁺ [M+H]⁺ 817.5140, found 817.1320. HR-MS (+): m/z calcd for C₂₀H₃₄Cl₂N₆O₁₂Pt + Na⁺ [M+Na]⁺ 839.4958, found 839.1130.

Cis,cis,trans-[Pt^{IV}(NH₃)₂(**20**)(OH)Cl₂] (**4**)

21 (0.075 g, 0.159 mmol) dissolved in dry DMSO (5 mL) was added dropwise, over 24 hr, to a suspension of oxoplatin (0.106 g, 0.318 mmol, 2 equiv.) in dry DMSO (7 mL) at 40°C. The reaction flask was heated at 40°C for a further 5 days before filtration of excess oxoplatin and removal of solvent via lyophilisation. The resulting oil was rinsed with the minimum amount of MeOH, washed with diethyl ether and dried in vacuo to yield the product as a pale yellow powder (0.043g, 0.062 mmol, 39%). ¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO) δ 8.34 (d, *J* = 8.5 Hz, 1H, NHCO), 7.82 (s, 1H, triaz-CH), 5.97 (t, 6H, 2x NH₃),

5.11 – 5.00 (m, 3H, NHCOCH_2 , OH of C-4), 4.94 (d, $J = 5.2$ Hz, 1H, OH of C-3), 4.63 – 4.49 (m, 2H, H-1, OH of C-6), 3.72 – 3.62 (m, 2H, H-2, H-6), 3.51 – 3.32 (m, 3H, H-6', H-3, H-5), 3.27 (s, 3H, OCH_3), 3.16 – 3.11 (m, 1H, H-4), 2.82 (t, $J = 7.5$ Hz, 2H, triaz- CH_2), 2.47 (t, $J = 7.6$ Hz, 2H, CH_2CO) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, DMSO) δ 179.98 (COOPt), 165.77 (CONH), 146.13 (triaz-C), 123.83 (triaz-CH), 97.79 (C-1), 72.81 (C-5), 70.89 (C-3), 70.68 (C-4), 60.80 (C-6), 54.39 (OCH_3), 54.06 (C-2), 51.47 (NHCOCH_2), 36.20 (CH_2CO), 21.96 (triaz- CH_2) ppm. $^{195}\text{Pt}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (108 MHz, DMSO) δ 1044.47 ppm. IR (ATR) 3256.68, 1676.10, 1559.39, 1021.64, 992.54 cm^{-1} . Elem. Anal. Calcd (%) for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{28}\text{Cl}_2\text{N}_6\text{O}_9\text{Pt}$: C: 24.36, H: 4.09, N: 12.17; found C: 24.76, H: 4.38, N: 12.48. HR-MS (+): m/z calcd for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{28}\text{Cl}_2\text{N}_6\text{O}_9\text{Pt} + \text{H}^+$ $[M+\text{H}]^+$ 690.1021, found 690.1102.

NMR Characterisation

^{13}C NMR spectrum of **7** in CDCl_3

COSY NMR spectrum of **7** in CDCl₃

HSQC NMR spectrum of **7** in CDCl₃

HMBC NMR spectrum of **7** in CDCl₃

^{13}C NMR spectrum of **14** in CDCl_3

COSY NMR spectrum of **14** in CDCl_3

HSQC NMR spectrum of **14** in CDCl_3

HMBC NMR spectrum of **14** in CDCl_3

^1H NMR spectrum of **15** in CDCl_3

^{13}C NMR spectrum of **15** in CDCl_3

COSY NMR spectrum of **15** in CDCl₃

HSQC NMR spectrum of **15** in CDCl₃

HMBC NMR spectrum of **15** in CDCl₃

^{13}C NMR spectrum of **17** in CDCl_3

COSY NMR spectrum of **17** in CDCl_3

HSQC NMR spectrum of **17** in CDCl_3

HMBC NMR spectrum of **17** in CDCl_3

^1H NMR spectrum of **18** in CDCl_3

^{13}C NMR spectrum of **18** in CDCl_3

COSY NMR spectrum of **18** in CDCl₃

HSQC NMR spectrum of **18** in CDCl₃

HMBC NMR spectrum of **18** in CDCl₃

HSQC NMR spectrum of **19** in CDCl_3

HMBC NMR spectrum of **19** in CDCl_3

^1H NMR spectrum of **20** in DMSO-d_6

^{13}C NMR spectrum of **20** in DMSO-d_6

COSY NMR spectrum of **20** in DMSO-d_6

HSQC NMR spectrum of **20** in DMSO-d_6

HMBC NMR spectrum of **20** in DMSO-d₆

¹H NMR spectrum of **21** in DMSO-d₆

¹³C NMR spectrum of **21** in DMSO-d₆

COSY NMR spectrum of **21** in DMSO-d₆

HSQC NMR spectrum of **21** in DMSO-d₆

HMBC NMR spectrum of **21** in DMSO-d₆

¹H NMR spectrum of complex 1 in DMSO-d₆

¹³C NMR spectrum of complex 1 in DMSO-d₆

COSY NMR spectrum of complex 1 in DMSO-d₆

HSQC NMR spectrum of **complex 1** in DMSO-d₆

HMBC NMR spectrum of **complex 1** in DMSO-d₆

¹⁹⁵Pt NMR spectrum of **complex 1** in DMSO-d₆

HSQC NMR spectrum of **complex 2** in DMSO-d₆

HMBC NMR spectrum of **complex 2** in DMSO-d₆

¹⁹⁵Pt NMR spectrum of **complex 2** in DMSO-d₆

¹H NMR spectrum of **complex 3** in DMSO-d₆

¹³C NMR spectrum of **complex 3** in DMSO-d₆

COSY NMR spectrum of **complex 3** in DMSO-d₆

HSQC NMR spectrum of **complex 3** in DMSO-d₆

HMBC NMR spectrum of **complex 3** in DMSO-d₆

¹⁹⁵Pt NMR spectrum of **complex 3** in DMSO-d₆

¹H NMR spectrum of **complex 4** in DMSO-d₆

¹³C NMR spectrum of **complex 4** in DMSO-d₆

COSY NMR spectrum of **complex 4** in DMSO-d₆

HSQC NMR spectrum of **complex 4** in DMSO-d₆

HMBC NMR spectrum of **complex 4** in DMSO-d₆

¹⁹⁵Pt NMR spectrum of **complex 4** in DMSO-d₆

Mass characterisation

HR-MS spectrum of **7**.

HR-MS spectrum of **8**.

HR-MS spectrum of **14**.

HR-MS spectrum of **15**.

HR-MS spectrum of **16**.

HR-MS spectrum of **17**.

HR-MS spectrum of **18**.

HR-MS spectrum of **19**.

HR-MS spectrum of **20**.

HR-MS spectrum of **21**.

HR-MS spectrum of **complex 1**.

HR-MS spectrum of **complex 2**.

HR-MS spectrum of **complex 3**.

HR-MS spectrum of **complex 4**.

Reduction studies

Complex 3: $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectra of the **complex 3** with addition of 10 eq. of ascorbic acid. NMR spectra were collected every 7 minutes for 60 minutes and then every hour for 3 hours and finally left to reduce for 3 days.

Complex 4: $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectra of the **complex 4** with addition of 10 eq. of ascorbic acid. NMR spectra were collected every 7 minutes for 60 minutes and then every hour for 2 hours and finally left to reduce for 1 day.